

Internal Temperature and Flux in Bound State Quantum and Classical Statistical Mechanics

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A number of people in the literature have described fluxes and continuity equations in quantum mechanics for non-bound state situations, i.e. complex wavefunctions. Their equations tend to zero if one inserts real wavefunctions. In this note, we wish to pursue some ideas of internal temperature and flux in a bound state quantum system (at overall temperature $T=0$), in particular density changing fluxes and compare the results to those of classical statistical mechanics.

Quasiparticles

It is possible to write the Schrodinger equation (1) as:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \int \sin(px)]/ W(x) + V(x) = E$$

This suggests that $\int \sin(px)/W(x)$ acts as a conditional probability $P(p/x)$. In addition, it was suggested in (2), that one could describe a quantum bound state as composed of quasiparticles defined by $W(x) \int \sin(px)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $W(x) = \text{Sum on } p \int \sin(px)$. By summing over p , one obtains $W(x)W(x)$, the density, and multiplying by $p^2/2m$ and summing over p , one obtains kinetic energy density. For odd powers of p , however, one must be careful as it seems that a meaningful result is $\text{Sum } W(x) \int \cos(px)$ or $W(x) d/dx W(x)$.

Thus, for odd powers of p , one cannot simply use $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ when forming an average.

It seems that $W(x) d/dx W(x)$ is a physically meaningful quantity as $d(x+b) = d(x) + b^2$

$W(x)d/dxW(x)$ where $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$ is the density. Thus, $W(x)d/dxW(x)$ measures changes in density and we try to describe it as a flux. We wish to examine this issue in more detail and so consider the case of no potential $V(x)=0$.

Case of No Potential $V(x)=0$

In the case of no potential, one has a Schrodinger equation of the form:

$$(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) = E W(x) \quad \text{where } E = p^2/2m \quad (\hbar=1)$$

A solution is $\sin(px)$ (which needs to be normalized). This can be thought of as a certain combination of a forward wave and a backward wave. Another math solution is $\cos(px)$. For simplicity, let us consider $\cos(px)$ (with a box centered at the origin and extending from $-L/2$ to $L/2$). Then one may think of $.5 \exp(ipx)/\cos(px)$ and $.5 \exp(-ipx)/\cos(px)$ as being conditional

probabilities for $P(p/x)$. Then, it is clearer to see how odd and even averages behave as one is summing over $+p$ and $-p$.

Consider the average of p :

$$P_{ave} = .5 \exp(ipx)/\cos(px) p + (-p) .5 \exp(-ipx)/\cos(px) = i p \sin(px)/\cos(px)$$

This strange average leads to an imaginary value, even for the bound state, but we suggest taking the magnitude. What is surprising is this flux can be positive and negative in different places, although its integral over x is 0. For classical mechanics and even classical statistical mechanics of an equilibrium situation, p_{ave} is 0 as forward and backward motion cancel. In quantum mechanics, it is suggested that particles are not points and that zitterbewegung is occurring allowing for a sinusoidal shape in space.

Let us now consider p^*p ave:

$$P^*P_{ave} = .5 \exp(ipx) p^*p / \cos(px) + (-p)^*(-p) \exp(ipx) .5 / \cos(px) = p^*p$$

Thus, $p^*p_{ave} = p^*p$, the classical result for all x in the box. Thus, one requires an interpretation for P_{ave} . As mentioned above, even in the case of no potential $V(x)$ quantum mechanics leads to a density $= W(x)W(x)$. It seems that p_{ave} , which seems by definition to be a flux, is a driver for this density because: $d(x+b) = d(x) + 2b W(x) dW(x)/dx$. P_{ave} is a strange flux because it changes sign. In some places $W(x)$ is increasing with x and the flux is positive, whereas in others $W(x)$ is decreasing and the flux is negative. In classical statistical mechanics, for equilibrium situations average velocity is 0 at each point, but density is still changing with x if there is a potential. Thus, $dW(x)/dx$ or rather $d d(x)/dx$ where $d(x)$ is the density may still be appropriate in the classical case. This is considered in a later section.

Quantum Bound Case with a Potential

The quantum bound case with a potential has been considered in (3). Here we wish to examine the strange results in a little more detail. First, it was suggested that one could define a temperature density which depends on x both through the changing temperature and density. It was suggested that one could use ideas from classical statistical mechanics to calculate this, namely (4)

$$u(x) = \langle v \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad T(x) = \langle |v-u|^2 \rangle$$

We suggest using $u = (1/W) dW/dx$, the strange flux velocity which changes the density as u . In classical statistical mechanics, it is noted that $u(x)=0$ for the equilibrium case (which is similar to the quantum bound state it seems).

$$\text{In such a case:} \quad T(x)d(x) = -W(x)(d/dx)(d/dx) W(x) - (d/dx W)^2 \quad ((1))$$

It seems that energy densities are physical quantities in quantum mechanics. Thus, ((1)) can be written as:

$$T(x) d(x) + W^*W(1/W dW/dx)^2 = .5 mv(x)*v(x) W(x)W(x) ((2))$$

Where the right hand side of ((2)) is the classical kinetic energy density equal to $(E-V(x)) W(x)W(x)$. Thus, the flux which changes density when squared and added to a temperature density (with temperature changing with x) yields the classical kinetic energy density. One might wonder why one would square a flux $1/W dW/dx$ in the first place, but if there is an average momentum flux at x , one might argue that there is an associated kinetic energy at x as well. The fact that this is not the same as the average of $p^*p/2m$ and that a temperature has to be added is interesting. The average of $p^*p/2m$ is also interesting as it is associated with the classical kinetic energy density, even for ground state quantum mechanical systems. For the quantum system, the classical kinetic energy density added to the potential $V(x)$ density and integrated gives the total energy. There is no apparent thermal energy. Quantum mechanics, however, has a peculiar density distribution and if one argues that this is created by a flux $(1/W)dW/dx$, one needs to add an internal temperature density to this flux density in order to obtain the classical kinetic energy density.

This is a completely different picture than that of cycling system creating an average kinetic energy $[\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m \ f_p \sin(px)]/W(x)$ at each point x such that this added to $V(x)$ gives E at each point. This strange flux, however, seems to also lead to a picture of periodic motion since the flux velocity is positive when the wavefunction is increasing and negative when it is decreasing. For wavefunctions with various humps, this flux is changing sign together with a changing temperature flux creating what looks like a kind of physical resonance.

What happens then for high energy eigenvalues, when the correspondence principle is to make peak points of the wavefunction look like the classical result. At a peak point, the density is sharp and so it is as if a particle is at x where the potential is $V(x)$ and the kinetic energy is $.5mv(x)v(x)$. At a peak point $dW/dx=0$, so the density changing flux is 0 at this point, meaning that the classical kinetic energy density is all temperature density energy according to ((2)).

Relation with Classical Statistical Mechanics

It was noted in (3), that for the case of $V(x)=.5kx*x$, the oscillator, the temperature defined in ((2)) is constant. Thus, the quantum case of an oscillator has constant temperature just as the classical statistical mechanical one. In addition, $W(x)$ and f_p are Gaussians of x and p , the same form as the classical statistical mechanics case. Finally, $W(x)W(x)V(x) = .5kx*x \exp(ax*x) = -C1 d(x) \ln(d(x))$ for the oscillator, i.e. it is equal to entropy. This has been considered in other notes (5).

A question remains as to the meaning of $(1/W) dW/dx$ for the classical statistical mechanical oscillator. In classical statistical mechanics, unlike quantum mechanics $\langle v \rangle = 0$ for the equilibrium case. In the quantum case, $u(x)$ was set to $(1/W) dW/dx$. This is completely different. On the other hand, in both quantum mechanics of the oscillator and classical statistical mechanics of

the same system, density changes in the same way (for the ground state). In fact, density changes whenever there is a potential $V(x)$ in classical statistical mechanics. Thus, one may suggest that:

$$1/d(x) d/dx d(x) \quad \text{where } d(x) \text{ is the spatial density ((4))}$$

has meaning in classical statistical mechanics. One can see that this "apparent" flux which changes density is equivalent to $d/dx \ln(d(x))$. It is known that:

$$d/dx \ln(d(x)) = - d/dx V(x)/T \quad ((5))$$

will yield a solution for $d(x)$ for classical statistical mechanics of the form $d(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. A question arises as to whether such an equation is related to flow equations. Consider the Euler equation of fluid mechanics in one dimension (4):

$$(d/dt + u d/dx) u(x) + 1/d(x) d/dx P(x) = F(x)/m \quad ((6))$$

For an equilibrium case in classical statistical mechanics $u(x) = 0$, $P(x) = d(x)T$ and $F(x) = -d/dx V(x)$. Thus, the Euler equation is exactly the same as ((5)) with $1/d(x) d/dx P(x)$ taking the form of the density changing flux from quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have examined issues related to internal temperature and density changing flux $1/W(x) d/dx W(x)$ (where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction) for the case of no potential $V(x)=0$ to see if the ideas still hold there which they seem to. We have again considered the case of $V(x)$ not zero to see that the classical kinetic energy density which appears in the time-independent Schrodinger equation is equivalent to the density of this "density changing flux" plus a temperature density. It seems that there is a kind of resonance occurring with the flux changing signs (and the temperature changing as well). For the case of an oscillator ground state, the quantum internal density is constant. We have examined the idea of $1/d(x) d/dx d(x)$ where $d(x)$ is density flux having relevance in classical statistical mechanics and it seems that it is, allowing for the calculation of the spatial density $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

References

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